

LOGICAL COMPONENT IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14275751>

Abstract. The author suggests that the acquisition of the content of basic logical training in the process of studying mathematical disciplines is most effectively carried out in the process of solving logic-oriented problems, in which the main emphasis is placed on the logical component of the educational material of the initial course of mathematics. The article provides examples of some problems in the section "Mathematical concepts, propositions, proofs" and reveals the content of the corresponding work of students.

Keywords: logic, logical training, mathematical training, primary school teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical training of primary education teachers at a university is a multifaceted and complex process aimed not only at mastering subject and methodological knowledge, skills and abilities, but also at developing professionally and personally significant qualities of a teacher, ensuring the effectiveness of his future professional activity. The goal of mathematical training is to provide a future primary school teacher with the necessary tools, the use of which in the practice of teaching younger students should contribute to their assimilation of the basic principles of mathematics, the formation of general ideas about the features of mathematical knowledge and mathematical language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this case, the most important tool of didactic influence on the student when teaching him mathematics are logical problems. In order for the didactic interaction of logic and mathematics in the process of teaching primary school students to be effective, it is necessary that the primary education teacher himself, in the process of his studies at the university, be purposefully prepared for this. Following V. I. Igoshin, by logical training of a future primary school teacher we will understand a specially organized purposeful process of forming logical knowledge and skills, skills in mastering the methods of logic "as a science about the laws and methods of correct thinking, reasoning and proof, acting as a tool in solving educational and professional problems" [1]. The

problem of logical training of future primary school teachers is insufficiently covered in scientific and methodological literature. Some of the first works devoted to the study of this problem in the context of school and university education belong to A. A. Stolyar and I. L. Nikolskaya. The problem of improving the logical training of teachers is the subject of the works of G. V. Dorofeev, L. D. Kudryavtsev, A. N. Kolmogorov, T. V. Morozov, S. A. Sevostyanov, I. L. Timofeeva, A. M. Sokhor, M. N. Alekseev and others [1-4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We are convinced that the logical training of future primary school teachers must be carried out in two stages:

- the basic stage of logical training, implemented within the framework of the disciplines "Mathematics", "Computer Science", "Theoretical Foundations of Mathematics", where an acquaintance with the elements of mathematical logic as a fundamental basis for constructing mathematical theories, statements and concepts takes place;

- a professionally oriented stage of logical training, implemented within the framework of disciplines not only of mathematics and natural sciences, but also of general professional and special cycles ("Methodology of Teaching Mathematics", "Computer Science and Methodology of Teaching Computer Science", "Fundamentals of Methods of Teaching Primary School Subjects", etc.), where students' attention is focused on issues that have deep logical significance for future pedagogical activity.

Thus, the basic logical training of a future primary school teacher organically develops into his professionally oriented logical training and as a result becomes the system-forming core of not only mathematical, but also general professional training of a teacher at a university. It is with such an organization of logical training that logical knowledge can become the foundation of the professional pedagogical worldview of a future primary school teacher.

The educational objectives at the stage of basic logical training of primary education teachers are: the formation of basic logical concepts and ideas in students; the development of skills and abilities in solving logical problems, as well as the ability of students to illustrate the studied material with examples from the basic course of mathematics.

When selecting the content of the basic logical training of primary education teachers, we proceeded from considerations of the expediency of developing knowledge and skills of logical thinking that will be in demand in

their educational and future professional activities. Thus, the content of the general logical training of future primary school teachers includes the following sections:

- elements of set theory;
- mathematical concepts, propositions, proofs;
- elements of stochastics;
- elements of the theory of algorithms.

These sections, presented to varying degrees in the primary school mathematics course, form the core of the basic logical training of the teacher.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the logical training of future primary school teachers, carried out first at the basic stage and then at the professionally oriented stage, becomes the system-forming core of not only mathematical, but also general professional training of a teacher at a university. Such a system of logical training allows students to be equipped with a system of logical-mathematical methods of cognition of the surrounding reality and to ensure their understanding of the scientific foundations of the initial course of mathematics, and also contributes to the improvement of logical-linguistic skills, consisting in the correct use of logical means and terms of mathematical language in accordance with the goals of pedagogical activity.

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